
THE ROLE OF INTERACTIVE ACTIVITIES IN DEVELOPING SPEAKING SKILLS OF
ELEMENTARY LEARNERS

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Annotation: Interactive activities are important for developing speaking skills of elementary learners. At this level, students often feel shy and have limited vocabulary, which makes speaking difficult. The aim of this article is to examine how interactive activities help improve speaking skills. The study focuses on activities such as role plays, pair work, and games. The results show that these activities increase student participation, confidence, and motivation. Students become more active and willing to speak in class. In conclusion, interactive activities are an effective way to develop speaking skills and create a positive learning environment.

Keywords: interactive activities, speaking skills, elementary learners, communication, classroom interaction, language teaching, student engagement.

Аннотация: Интерактивные виды деятельности играют важную роль в развитии навыков говорения у учащихся начального уровня. На этом этапе учащиеся часто испытывают застенчивость и имеют ограниченный словарный запас, что затрудняет устную речь. Цель данной статьи рассмотреть, как интерактивные задания способствуют развитию навыков говорения. Исследование сосредоточено на таких видах деятельности, как ролевые игры, работа в парах и игровые задания. Результаты показывают, что эти методы повышают активность, уверенность и мотивацию учащихся. Студенты становятся более активными и готовыми к устному общению на занятиях. В заключение отмечается, что интерактивные методы являются эффективным средством развития навыков говорения и создания благоприятной учебной среды.

Ключевые слова: интерактивные задания, навыки говорения, учащиеся начального уровня, коммуникация, взаимодействие в классе, обучение языку, вовлечённость учащихся.

Annotatsiya: Interaktiv faoliyatlar boshlang‘ich darajadagi o‘quvchilarning gapirish ko‘nikmalarini rivojlantirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Bu bosqichda o‘quvchilar ko‘pincha tortinchoq bo‘ladi va ularning lug‘at boyligi cheklangan bo‘lib, bu gapirishni qiyinlashtiradi. Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi interaktiv faoliyatlar gapirish ko‘nikmalarini qanday rivojlantirishini tahlil qilishdir. Tadqiqot rolli o‘yinlar, juftlikda ishlash va o‘yinlar kabi faoliyatlarga qaratilgan. Natijalar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, bu faoliyatlar o‘quvchilarning faolligini, o‘ziga ishonchini va motivatsiyasini oshiradi. O‘quvchilar darslarda yanada faol bo‘lib, gapirishga ko‘proq intilishadi. Xulosa qilib aytganda, interaktiv faoliyatlar gapirish ko‘nikmalarini rivojlantirish va ijobiy o‘quv muhitini yaratishda samarali usul hisoblanadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: interaktiv faoliyatlar, gapirish ko‘nikmalari, boshlang‘ich darajadagi o‘quvchilar, muloqot, sinfdagi o‘zaro aloqa, til o‘qitish, o‘quvchi faolligi.

Introduction. Developing speaking skills is one of the main goals of learning a foreign language. For elementary learners, speaking is often the most challenging skill because they have limited vocabulary and basic grammar knowledge. Many students feel nervous when they speak and are afraid of making mistakes.

Traditional teaching methods sometimes focus more on grammar and writing than on communication. As a result, students may understand the language but cannot use it in real-life situations. This shows the need for more interactive and student-centered approaches in the classroom. Interactive activities such as role plays, pair work, and group discussions provide learners with opportunities to use language actively. These activities create a natural environment for communication and help students practice speaking in a meaningful way.

In my opinion, interactive activities are especially important for elementary learners because they make learning more enjoyable and reduce anxiety. When students are actively involved, they become more confident and motivated to speak.

The purpose of this article is to explore the role of interactive activities in developing speaking skills of elementary learners and to show how these methods can improve language learning.

Literature Review. According to H. D. Brown, speaking is an interactive process that requires both linguistic knowledge and the ability to use language in real situations. The author explains that learners develop speaking skills more effectively when they are actively involved in communication. Brown also emphasizes that meaningful interaction helps students practice language naturally and improves both fluency and confidence. This shows that speaking cannot be developed through passive learning, but requires active participation.¹

According to J. Harmer, interactive activities play a key role in language teaching, especially in developing speaking skills. The author notes that activities such as role plays, pair work, and group discussions create opportunities for real communication in the classroom. These activities help learners use language in context and reduce fear of speaking. Harmer also highlights that a supportive classroom environment encourages students to take risks and participate more actively.²

According to P. Ur, one of the main problems in teaching speaking is low student participation. The author explains that many learners remain passive because they lack confidence or do not understand what to do. Ur suggests that interactive and simple tasks can help involve all students in the lesson. Clear instructions and engaging activities make students more willing to speak and practice. This shows that teaching strategies are essential in overcoming speaking difficulties.³

In my opinion, these studies clearly show that interactive activities are not optional but necessary for developing speaking skills. When students are actively engaged, they feel more confident and motivated, which leads to better learning outcomes.

Methodology. This study uses a qualitative approach to examine the role of interactive activities in developing speaking skills of elementary learners. The aim is to understand how different activities influence student participation and speaking performance.

First, theoretical sources on language teaching and interactive methods were reviewed to identify key concepts. Then, classroom activities such as pair work, role plays, and games were observed and analyzed. The focus was on student engagement, participation, and improvement in speaking.

The data were analyzed descriptively to identify common patterns and effective strategies. In my opinion, this method helps connect theory with real classroom practice and provides practical insights for improving speaking skills.

Analysis and Results. The results of the study show that interactive activities have a positive effect on developing speaking skills of elementary learners. Students who participate in activities such as pair work, role plays, and games are more active and willing to speak. These

¹ Brown H. D. *Principles of Language Learning and Teaching*. – New York: Pearson Education, 2007. – 270–272 p.

² Harmer J. *How to Teach English*. – London: Longman, 2007. – 123–125 p.

³ Ur P. *A Course in English Language Teaching*. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2012. – 120–122 p.

activities create a comfortable environment where learners feel less afraid of making mistakes. One important finding is that pair work helps students practice speaking more frequently. Instead of waiting for their turn, learners can speak at the same time with their partners. For example, simple question–answer tasks like “*What is your favorite food?*” or “*What do you do every day?*” allow students to use basic vocabulary and structures in real communication.

Another effective activity is role play. In this activity, students take roles such as a customer and a shop assistant or a teacher and a student. This helps them practice everyday conversations in a meaningful context. For example, acting out a situation like “buying something in a shop” encourages students to use language naturally and confidently. Games also play an important role in developing speaking skills. Activities such as guessing games or picture description tasks make learning more enjoyable and reduce anxiety. When students are engaged in games, they focus less on mistakes and more on communication. In my opinion, these activities are effective because they give students more opportunities to speak and practice language in real situations. They also increase motivation and make the learning process more interactive. Overall, the results show that interactive activities help improve both confidence and speaking ability of elementary learners.

Discussion. The findings confirm that interactive activities play a crucial role in developing speaking skills of elementary learners. Unlike traditional methods that focus mainly on grammar and passive learning, interactive tasks create opportunities for real communication. Through activities such as pair work, role plays, and games, students become more engaged and are able to practice language in meaningful contexts.

Another important point is that interactive activities help reduce psychological barriers. Elementary learners often feel anxious and afraid of making mistakes, which limits their participation. However, when they are involved in communicative tasks, they feel more relaxed and confident. This shows that a supportive and interactive classroom environment is essential for effective speaking development.

From my perspective, the success of these activities lies in their ability to combine practice with motivation. When students enjoy the activity, they are more willing to speak and take risks. Therefore, teachers should carefully select and adapt activities according to learners’ level and needs in order to achieve better results.

Conclusion. In conclusion, this study demonstrates that interactive activities are an effective means of developing speaking skills in elementary learners. They not only improve linguistic competence but also increase student confidence and participation. The results highlight that speaking skills can be developed more successfully when learners are given regular opportunities to communicate in a supportive environment. Interactive methods such as pair work, role play, and games make the learning process more dynamic and meaningful. Overall, the use of interactive activities should be considered an essential part of language teaching at the elementary level. By focusing on communication and student engagement, teachers can help learners overcome their difficulties and achieve better outcomes in speaking.

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